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Review Article

**REVIEW ARTICLE ON QUALITY AUDIT IN
PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS**N.Sravani ^{1*}, Ch.V.Suresh², S.Venu³, D.Naveen³, M.Prasanthi³, E.Jhansi³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu (Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.²Principal, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.³Research Scholar, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.**Abstract:**

Quality audit is a key management tool for monitoring the suitability of a company's quality management system and in driving continuous improvement leading to Good manufacturing practice compliance and inspection readiness. Conducting internal audits and external audits of suppliers and outsourcing operations are key elements of a good quality system. Auditing in the pharmaceutical sector serves two different categories: regulatory compliance and business needs. By establishing a high-quality audit system throughout the industry, the level of compliance will increase. This article explores the establishment of an auditing program for both internal audits and external audits including key elements to address when implementing an auditing program. Auditing is a dynamic part of any pharmaceutical companies. Quality Audit is analysis and appraisal of all quality assurance program and quality control program to ensure its quality. It is one of the way to examine pharmacy program and make sure that procedures, compensation comply with regulatory and GMP requirements. Quality audit is usually operated by external experts or by a team selected by management of pharmaceutical companies. An audit will appraise strength and weakness of quality assurance processes, the result will help in improving the process and also build better system for company benefits. Pharmaceutical audits includes from design qualification upto performance qualification steps. It also included SOP, guildliness, validation policies.

Keywords: Audit; Internal audit; SOP; Nonconformities; Defects**Corresponding author:****N.Sravani,**Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet,
Palnadu (Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Quality audit is the process of systematic examination of a quality system carried out by an internal or external quality auditor or an audit team¹. It is an important part of organization's quality management system and is a key element in the ISO quality system standard, ISO 9001.

Quality audits are typically performed at predefined time intervals and ensure that the institution has clearly defined internal system monitoring procedures linked to effective action. With the upgrade of the ISO9000 series of standards, the focus of the audits has shifted from purely procedural adherence towards measurement of the actual effectiveness of the Quality Management System (QMS) and the results that have been achieved through the implementation of a QMS.

Audits are an essential management tool to be used for verifying objective evidence of processes, to assess how successfully processes have been implemented, for judging the effectiveness of achieving any defined target levels, to provide evidence concerning reduction and elimination of problem areas². For the benefit of the organization, quality auditing should not only report non-conformances and corrective actions, but also highlight areas of good practice. **Quality audit: It** is defined as periodic independent documented examination and verification of activities, records, processes and other elements of a quality system to determine their conformity with the requirements of a quality standard such as ISO 9000.

Any failure in their proper implementation may be published publicly and may lead to a revocation of quality certification. It is also called as **conformity assessment** or **quality system audit**.

QUALITY AUDIT BENEFITS³

- It drives continuous improvement.
- It lets the management know problems or potential problems.
- Shift activities from reactive to proactive.
- Facilitates self evaluation.
- Provides input into management decisions.
- Accesses training and effectiveness.
- Shows management support of the quality program.
- Verifies compliance.

QUALITY AUDITOR³

The Certified Quality Auditor is a professional who understands the standards and principles of auditing and the auditing techniques of examining, questioning, evaluating and reporting to determine a quality system's adequacy and deficiencies.

Quality Auditor analyzes all elements of a quality system and judges its degree of adherence to the criteria of industrial management, quality evaluation and control systems.

Auditors must:

- Have integrity and be independent and objective.
- Have the authority they need to do a proper job.
- Avoid compromising the audit by discussing audit details with auditees during the audit.

OBJECTIVES OF QUALITY AUDIT³

Quality audits are intended to achieve the following kinds of objectives:

- To determine to what extent your quality system.
- Achieves its objectives.
- Conforms to your requirements.
- Complies with regulatory requirements.
- Meets customers' contractual requirements.
- Conforms to a recognized quality standard.
- To improve the efficiency and effectiveness of your quality management system.
- To list your quality system in registry of an independent agency.
- To verify that your quality system continues to meet requirements.

THE PRINCIPLE BEHIND QUALITY AUDIT⁴

- The principle is that each organization should create thorough, controlled procedures for each of its processes. Those procedures should deliver the quality that is sought.
- The Quality Audit, therefore, only needs to ensure that procedures have been defined, controlled, communicated and used.
- Processes will be put in place to deal with corrective actions when deviations occur. This principle can be applied to continuous business process operations or recurring project work.

OPERATING QUALITY AUDIT⁵

A Quality Audit approach affects the entire work lifecycle

- Pre-defined standards will impact the way the project is planned
- Quality requirements for specific work packages and deliverables will be identified in advance
- Specific procedures will be followed at all stages
- Quality Methods must be defined and followed
- Completed work and deliverables should be reviewed for compliance.

This should be seen as an underlying framework and set of rules to apply in the project's Quality Management processes.

PREPARING FOR QUALITY AUDIT

Thorough procedures need to be defined, controlled, communicated and used.

Thorough	Procedures should cover all aspects of work where conformity and standards are required to achieve desired quality levels.
Procedures	Any recurring aspect of work could merit regulation. The style and depth of the description will vary according to needs and preferences, provided it is sufficiently clear to be followed.
Defined	A major tenet is that the defined procedures are good and will lead to the desired levels of quality. Considerable thought, consultation and trialing should be applied in order to define appropriate procedures. Procedures will often also require defined forms or software tools.
Controlled	As with any good quality management, the procedures should be properly controlled in terms of accessibility, version control, update authorities etc.
Communicated	All participants need to know about the defined procedures that they exist, where to find them, what they cover. Quality reviewers are likely to check that team members understand about the procedures.
Used	The defined procedures should be followed. Checks will be made to ensure this is the case. A corrective action procedure will be applied to deal with shortcomings. Typically the corrective action would either be to learn the lesson for next time, or to re-work the item if it is sufficiently important.

SCOPE OF QUALITY AUDIT ⁶

- To define the scope of the audit is to define the boundaries.
- The client or audit authority is responsible for defining the scope of the audit, and makes the final decisions on the scope and depth of the audit.
- Quality system elements, physical locations, and organizational activities are to be audited within a specified time frame.
- Establishing the scope is necessary for the audit planning.

AREAS SUBJECTED TO QUALITY AUDIT ⁶

- Virtually every phase of operations impacting on the quality and safety of product manufactured, packaged, stored and distributed should be subjected to audit.
- Audits are sometimes conducted on a product basis, but more often by operational area, function or department.

- The auditing of perceived trouble spots could result in over looking problem in pre conceived trouble free areas. This can be avoided by conducting checks and randomly selected areas.

STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE FOR AUDITS ⁷

A written SOP covering audit should be prepared.

1. To spell out company policy regarding audits
2. A statement of the purpose and scope of audits
3. Composition of audit team together with an outline of their authority and responsibility.
4. Areas subjected to auditing
5. Frequency of audits
6. Written records on audits including their distribution.
7. Corrective action to be taken as a result of deficiencies uncovered during audits including time tables and provisions for follow-ups and specific responsibilities for achieving corrections when required and provision for re-audits when appropriate.

AUDIT PURPOSE⁷

1. **Contract award and agreements to purchase**
 - There is a need to investigate and report on the management systems of a new supplier.
 - The objective would be to determine their capabilities to effectively control their processes and implement adequate and timely corrective actions.
2. **Investment in supplier based tooling**
 - There has been a general or product specific decline in supplier quality.
 - The objective would be to discover the cause.
3. **Continued involvement with a supplier**
 - Periodic, routine surveillance or maintenance audits are performed as part of the client company's quality assurance systems.
 - The objective would be to verify that suppliers are implementing high quality standards and supporting their established systems.

AUDIT ORGANIZATION⁷**1. Client**

- The client is responsible for defining the goals and objectives of the audit.
- Client is a reference to either the company or organization requesting the performance of the audit.
- Client has the authority to require that an audit be performed and the recipient of the audit report.

A client's job is to:

- Initiate the audit process.
- Select the auditor organization.
- Decide whether an audit needs to be done.
- Define the purpose and scope of the audit.
- Ensure that audit resources are adequate.
- Determine how often audits must be done.
- Specify which follow-up actions the auditee should take.
- Indicate which standards should be used to evaluate compliance.
- Select the elements, activities, and locations that must be audited.
- Ensure enough evidence is collected to draw valid conclusions.
- Receive and review the reports prepared by auditors.

2. The quality assurance manager

- The quality assurance manager is usually assigned the responsibility for the administration of the audit program.
- An unscheduled or scheduled audit should be documented and approved by the audit authority.
A lead auditor's job is to:
 - Provide leadership and support to the audit group.
 - Provide for adequate auditor skills training.
 - Provide escorts when the company is the subject of an audit.
 - Assign audit tasks.
 - Help select auditors.
 - Orient the audit team.
 - Prepare the audit plan.
 - Clarify and communicate quality audit requirements.
 - Prepare audit forms and checklists.
 - Review quality system documents.
 - Report major nonconformities immediately.
 - Interact with auditee's management and staff.
 - Prepare, submit, and discuss audit reports.

3. The audit team leader

- He is the Lead auditor.
- The audit team leader is responsible for carrying out the goals and objectives of the audit program as directed.

An auditor's job is to:

- Evaluate the quality system.
- Carry out assigned audit tasks.
- Comply with audit requirements.
- Respect all confidentiality requirements.
- Collect evidence about the quality system.
- Document audit observations and conclusions.
- Safeguard audit documents, records, and reports.
- Determine whether quality policy is being applied.
- Find out if the quality objectives are being achieved.
- See whether quality procedures are being followed.
- Detect evidence that might invalidate audit results.

TYPES OF QUALITY AUDITS⁸

1. Product Audit
2. Process Audit
3. Systems Audit
4. Internal Audit - (First Party)

5. External Audit - (Second or Third Party)
6. Specific Objective Audits

1. Product Audit

The product audit is an in-depth examination of a particular product or service to evaluate whether it conforms to product specifications, performance standards, and customer requirements.

Product audit may be performed in two ways:

- Internally: An example is a dock, where product is examined and tested prior to shipment.
- Externally: The audit may be conducted at the customer site, or with the final customer.

2. Process Audit

It is an analysis of elements of a process, appraisal of completeness, correctness of conditions and probable effectiveness.

Characteristics of process audit are

- Usually concentrate on one or more specific product or service processes.
- May be performed internally or externally.
- Require less planning than the system audit.
- Can be very helpful in improving the process of concern

3. Systems Audit

A system audit is the largest and most extensive of audits. System audit are conducted to verify, through objective evidence, whether or not the quality system management systems and organizational plans are indeed carried out to the requirements set forth.

A system audit may be conducted as a condition of accepting a new supplier prior to contract award. This is called a pre-award survey.

4. Internal Audit

An internal audit is performed within an organization to measure its strengths and weaknesses against its own procedures or methods and/or external standards adopted by the auditee organization (voluntary) or imposed on the auditee organization (mandatory).

- An internal audit is considered to be a **first party audit**.

Internal audits are of two types: Internal system audits and Internal performance audits

Internal system audits:

The simplest type of internal system audit consists of an ongoing supervisory surveillance of the quality assurance practices of sub ordinates. Periodic notebook checks are an example of a routine audit of procedural details. Supervisors are ordinarily responsible for assuring that GLPs, GMPs and SOPs are followed and a systematic procedure to ascertain this may be considered as an internal audit.

Internal performance audit:

It essentially consists of reviewing the ongoing quality assessment program of a laboratory. Its objective should be to evaluate the accuracy of all data. The status of reference and samples are checked.

Salient principles of internal audits

- It is performed in accordance with written procedures
- It should be documented in written reports
- It should be performed by appropriately trained individuals who do not have direct responsibilities for the matters being audited.
- Copies of the reports should be submitted to management.
- Follow-up corrective action is taken as appropriate
- The deficient matters are re-audited as indicated.

Objectives of internal audits

- One of the most important objectives of an internal quality audit is measuring the effectiveness of an organizations quality management system.
- The main purpose of studying one's own operations through audits is to identify problems so that corrective actions can be taken, thus avoiding regulatory actions.

5. External Audit

An external audit is an audit performed by company directive on an outside source, such as a supplier. Product knowledge, contracts, purchase agreements, and secrecy agreements make it most common that the company conducting the audit sends personnel from its own auditing staff to perform an external audit.

- An external audit is considered to be a **second party audit**.

- It may be also sometimes considered as a **third party audit** when an outside source or a third party other than the customer is used to conduct the audit. The third party audit is used to obtain a more independent and objective assessment, or to achieve certification to a recognized standard.

6. Specific Objective Audit: These are again divided into 4 types.

➤ Assessments

- Assessments are quality audits, sometimes indicating a less formal means of measuring and reporting than with normal audits.
- An assessment is usually limited in scope and may be performed during contracting phase and executing phase.

➤ Pre-Award Surveys

- These are system audits which may be conducted as a condition of accepting a new supplier prior to contract award.
- The purpose of the pre-award survey is to evaluate the ability of the potential supplier to provide a product or service which meets requirements and determine what, if any assistance might be needed.

➤ Quality System Reviews

- These are system audits resulting from significant changes which may affect product quality.
- This type of audit may be necessary if product quality deteriorates or if there are critical changes in management.

➤ Compliance Audit

- Compliance audit is designed to provide assurance that defined or specified activities have been performed properly.
- These audits verify whether or not the systems, processes or products satisfy the requirements as set forth in the contracted agreements, procedures or standard.

DESIGN REVIEW: DOCUMENTATION ⁹

1. Quality Manual

- A quality manual is a formal and authorized document setting out the quality policies, systems, procedures and practice of a organization.
- It identifies the responsibilities, authorities, and inter-relationships of personnel, who manage, perform, verify or review work affecting quality.

2. Procedures

- Procedures are written documents that specify the purpose and scope of an activity.
- What is to be done, where, and by whom.

3. Work instructions

- Work instructions expand on procedures by adding how and when an activity must be done, controlled and recorded.
- They indicate what materials, equipment and documents are to be used.

AUDIT COMPONENTS ¹⁰

1. Audit planning
2. Audit performance
3. Audit reporting
4. Corrective action or follow up phase

1. Audit planning

- The audit plan should contain:
 - The objectives and scope of the audit.
 - Explain how long each phase of the audit will take.
 - Specify where and when the audit will be carried out.
 - Introduce the lead auditor and his team members.
 - Identify the quality elements that will be audited.
 - Identify the groups and areas that will be audited.
 - List the documents and records that will be studied.
 - List the people who are responsible for quality and whose areas and functions will be audited.
 - Explain when meetings will be held with auditee's senior management.
 - Clarify who will get the final audit report and when it will be ready.
 - The working documents are accumulated during the preparation phase and may include
 - Checklists.
 - Reporting forms.
 - Quality manual.
 - Quality system procedures.
 - Quality system work instructions.

2. Audit Performance (Execution)

- The performance phase begins with the on-site opening meeting and includes the gathering of information and analysis of that information.
- Normally this is accomplished by conducting interviews, monitoring activities, and examining items and records.

- General audit performance procedure includes **8 stages**:

i. Preparation

The auditor or the auditing team enters the information required in the heading of the audit form. In designating the level of audit, a material code identified by the code, the serial numbers of the appropriate documents are entered in the spaces indicated in audit form. Finally, auditors check off which elements of the system are to be audited.

ii. First notification

A copy of the audit form is presented to the manager responsible for the department or section to be audited as notification of audit.

iii. Examination

Operation and control standards documented should be examined to ensure that they are current. Whenever possible, observed departures from operating and control standards should be corrected during the course of examination.

iv. Second notification

Upon completion of examination, the auditors sign the original of the form and present a copy to the department or section manager. This constitutes a notification that the auditors want to meet the department or section management to discuss findings and recommend actions.

v. Evaluation

Findings and recommended actions are evaluated

vi. Referral

Where there is a disagreement or where the implementation of recommended action exceeds a manager's approval authority, the specific item is referred to higher levels of management. The mechanism for receiving, reviewing and deciding on such referrals might be multi discipline plant process committees, material review boards etc, whose authority are spelled out in policy statements or procedures.

vii. Conformance report

After completion of all actions not under referral, a conformance report is prepared by the auditors and placed in the batch.

viii. Final notification

Upon completion and filling of the conformance report, the department or section manager and the local quality assurance manager sign the

original audit form and distribute the copies as indicated on the form to notify the recipients that the audited systems elements are in conformance.

3. Audit Reporting:¹¹

- The audit report is the official document which covers the translation of the audit team's findings and conclusions into a formal audit report.

- It is generally accepted that the audit report should be accurate, concise, clear, and timely (mailed within one week)

- The audit report should :

- Be dated and signed by the lead auditor.
- Contain the scope and objectives of the audit.
- Contain details of the audit plan.
- Identify the audit team and the auditee's representative.
- List audit dates.
- Identify the specific organization audited.
- Describe observations of nonconformities.
- Express a judgment of the extent of the auditee's compliance.

- The reporting phase covers the following activities.

- Prioritize the audit results.
- Preparing the audit report.
- Listing findings and observations.
- Including corrective action requests and responses dates
- Expressing a judgment of the extent of auditee's compliance.
- Approving the report.
- Distributing the report to the auditee, client, and official files.
- Retaining audit records.

Submission of audit report:

The lead auditor should send the audit report to the client, and the client should send it to the auditee.

4. Corrective Action or Follow up Phase:¹²

- The auditee is responsible for providing the lead auditor with a corrective action plan within a specified time frame.

- The plan will outline the actions to be taken to rectify the non-conformance; the individuals assigned and estimated date of completion.

- Some form of formal closure criteria should be stipulated by the auditee through whom the

auditor can verify successful implementation during the follow up audit.

- Corrective action and subsequent follow-up audit should be completed within a time period agreed to by the client and the auditee in consultation with the auditing organization.

QUALITY AUDIT LIMITATIONS:¹³⁻¹⁴

These limitations prevent an effective audit.

- Finding faults and not facts
- Not properly defining the purpose and scope.
- Not using a quality audit checklist
- Not issuing a corrective action.
- Not conducting follow up on the corrective action.
- Not using a team approach to issuing corrective actions

CONCLUSION:

Achieving excellence quality is a primary goal of business and companies around the world. In order to achieve this goal, individual need to understand how to evaluate quality systems and use auditing as management tools for fostering ongoing improvement.

A well planned and comprehensive quality audit program covers each area of the service and also assesses the way in which its different components relate to each other. Audits are essential to maintain, strengthen and improve quality. Thus, they are viewed as “**improvement opportunities**”.

REFERENCES:

1. Shital V. Sirsat . A Brief Review On: Pharmaceutical Audit Guide', International Journal of Current Advanced Research, 2022;11(07):1248-1254.
2. Kannan S, Morais SR, Prema S, Chitra K. Auditing as a management tool in pharmaceutical companies. International Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences. 2020;10(1):230-5.

3. Kumar S, Tanwar D, Arora N. The role of regulatory GMP audit in pharmaceutical companies. Int J Res Dev Pharm Life Sci. 2013;2:493-8.
4. Yogesh Waghmare and Sonali Mahaparale; A Review Article of Self Inspection and Internal Audit; European Journal Of Pharmaceutical And Medical Research; EJPMR, 2017,4(7), 358-364.
5. Vedanabhata S, Gupta VN. A review on audits and compliance management. Asian J Pharm Clin Res 2013;6:43-51.
6. Agarwal PR, Mishra AM. Pharmaceutical quality audits a review. Int J Appl Pharm. 2019;11:14-22.
7. Gaikwad PH, Jadhav AG, Pathan VT, Gujarati NA. Review On Vendor Audit Management. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development. 2018; 23;6(4):92-6.
8. Nedelcheva Y. Internal Audit in the Pharmaceutical Sector: International and National Good Practices. Journal Aktiv. 2014 ;1;13-5.
9. Christopher J, Sarens G, Leung P. A critical analysis of the independence of the internal audit function: evidence from Australia. Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal. 2009 ;22(2):200-20.
10. Zhou H, Owusu-Ansah S, Maggina A. Board of directors, audit committee, and firm performance: Evidence from Greece. Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation. 2018;31:20-36.
11. Krishnan J. Audit committee quality and internal control: An empirical analysis. The accounting review. 2005;80(2):649-75.
12. Sarens G, De Beelde I. The relationship between internal audit and senior management: A qualitative analysis of expectations and perceptions. International Journal of Auditing. 2006;10(3):219-41.
13. Mihret DG, Admassu MA. Reliance of external auditors on internal audit work: A corporate governance perspective. International business research. 2011;4(2):67-79.
14. Seoane PJ. Use and limitations of checklists. Other strategies for audits and inspections. The Quality Assurance Journal: The Quality Assurance Journal for Pharmaceutical, Health and Environmental Professionals. 2001;5(3):133-6.